

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D6.1 Dissemination Strategy

WP6 - Dissemination and
Communication
Version: 2.00

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Executive Summary

The CALIPER project aims at driving a structural change process and implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in 7 Research Performing (UZG, STU, ULB, NTUA, IRB, YU, UNILE) and 2 Research Funding (SRNSF, UEFIS) organizations, involving the highest and middle management levels since the beginning to impact the whole institution. The project goal is to make research organizations more gender equal by increasing the number of female researchers in STEM, improving their careers prospects and integrating a gender dimension in research.

The dissemination and communication of the project constitute a pivotal aspect of its overall planning, due to their role on promoting CALIPER's intentions, scope and contributions to the purpose of gender equality. Hence, the project adopts a multifaceted and detailed dissemination plan from the very beginning in order to:

- Create awareness about the CALIPER project and the Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) to be developed.
- Increase engagement and encourage involvement of the target groups in the project activities.
- Promote sustainability and the best practises of CALIPER actions after the project's completion.

The aim is to put in place all necessary actions to achieve the desired outcomes, provide guidelines to partners about the implementation of dissemination and training tasks through a coherent, structured and effective approach, while it monitors dissemination and communication activities to properly adjust their implementation if necessary.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The current deliverable aims to present the design of the Dissemination Strategy that CALIPER is going to employ to achieve gender balance awareness, impact at both internal level of the involved RPOs/RFOs and external level including the target audiences of Stakeholders, as well as facilitation of the sustainability prospects of the project's results.

In order to define the most adequate methods to disseminate and communicate CALIPER this document refers to the strategy's objectives, key messages, the target audiences of the project and the Consortium partners' role outlining the Dissemination Strategy.

In this context, the present report:

- describes the dissemination approach,
- elaborates on the goals and the key messages established and disseminated during project
- identifies stakeholders that constitute the project's target audience,
- explains the tools, methods and channels to be used,
- addresses the role of the Consortium partners to the dissemination of the project
- provides the monitoring and evaluation procedures for the above design and
- sets the ground to ensure the project's sustainability after its completion.

This strategy will be reviewed and updated on a regular basis for assessing new and possible dissemination opportunities that may emerge during the project. As a result, the Dissemination Strategy will be updated following the reporting of activities, that is, in M15 "Dissemination and communication activities Report v1" (March 2021), in M30 "Dissemination Activities Report v2" (June 2022), in M48 "Dissemination Activities Report v3" (December 2023).

1.2 Intended Audience

This deliverable is dedicated on elaborating the overall dissemination and communication course that CALIPER has to follow. ViLabs is the Lead beneficiary of WP6 of Dissemination and Communication, while ULB and YAE are also leading Tasks, however, this WP necessitates efforts from each and every partner of the CALIPER Consortium. Therefore, it is essential that the Consortium Partners are well informed about the Dissemination Strategy, meaning that, the intended audience of the present strategy are the actual Organisations involved to the Project.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The present deliverable is organized in the following sections:

The first main section begins with a presentation of the project's Dissemination Strategy approach; it then enlists its objectives and incorporated messages. It proceeds on mapping the target audiences of CALIPER, as well as the Stakeholders communities that should be engaged with the project. Following this, the deliverable enlists the tools, methods and channels that will be used, and explains the Partners role in the overall dissemination and communication actions.

This section is followed by the presentation of project's monitoring and evaluation procedures, which intend to facilitate an accurate reporting and assessment of the dissemination and communication activities, clarify the procedures assigned to each project partner and secure that a sufficient understanding of the Dissemination Strategy impact will be attained.

1.4 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The Dissemination Strategy draws from, while also feeds into, the overall actions of the project since in many occasions they will provide useful content to be disseminated. What is more, there is a pivotal correlation between the dissemination and communication of CALIPER with the specific engagement procedures, elaborated on the Grant Agreement of the project. Due to the mutual objectives that these aspects have in terms of Stakeholders engagement the Dissemination Strategy is directly related to the WP5 of Engagement, Change Management and Sustainability. Detailed elaboration on this relation is addressed later on this report.

2 Dissemination Strategy

Dissemination aims at raising awareness and maximizing the outreach of the CALIPER results thereby contributing to developing sustainable GEPs and achieving structural changes. The target is to ensure that information is shared with appropriate audiences on a timely basis and by the most effective means finding potential collaborators to ensure the optimal use and institutionalization of the CALIPER results and speed up the potential of expansion and adoption by other RPOs/RFOs.

Emphasis is also given to provide detailed elaboration on the projected dissemination and communication activities, since all project partners are involved in order to foster awareness and transfer results to achieve impact, especially in their own innovation ecosystems.

At this point it is significant to underline that according to the Grant Agreement of Horizon2020, dissemination and communication activities are referred to different Articles, which means that, even though they may overlap and fuel each other, they feature some distinctive characteristics between them.

Article 29 states that **dissemination consists of disclosing a project's results** to third parties by appropriate means, while the protection of data and inner-project confidentiality are respected. Using scientific publications and other similar mediums project partners have to circulate knowledge among stakeholders that can make use of such knowledge, thus enabling the value of project's results to be potentially wider than the original focus. Hence, the dissemination procedures seek to share material mainly with organisations relevant to the project, such as **research institutes, policy makers, NGOs, corporations, associations, etc.** who can exploit the results of the project. Because dissemination aims at the same direction as exploitation, the content is more specific and scientific. Dissemination includes various **reports created during the project, conference presentations, workshops, newsletters to Stakeholders, synergies with EU-related projects and more.**

Article 38.1 states that **communication has to promote both project's actions and its results** by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in strategic and effective methods. Partners have to deploy a communication campaign throughout a project's duration, in order to make the research activities known publicly **in a way that such actions can be understood by non-specialist audience.** Also, the communication activities must address the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding, by considering aspects such as the transnational cooperation in a European consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed to achieve more than otherwise possible), or the scientific excellence and the contribution to solving societal challenges. Communication includes **media publications about CALIPER's aspects, press releases and newsletters, social media promotion, offline and tangible material like posters and brochures.**

Bearing in mind the above, CALIPER's Dissemination Strategy incorporates both actions into its planning, while it pays attention on making the adequate distinctions between them according to the properties of the target audiences and the desired goals. Hence, the present report is structured following the **6W's approach**, a set of questions which outlines the below:

- **Why** to disseminate and communicate?
- **What** to disseminate and communicate?
- Disseminate and Communicate to **Whom**?
- Disseminate and Communicate **How**?
- Disseminate and Communicate **Where**?
- Disseminate and Communicate **When**?

The following sub-chapters elaborate on the enlisted questions to provide a detailed overview about the plan of CALIPER dissemination and communication.

2.1 Objectives

This part is set to provide context regarding **why CALIPER needs to be disseminated and communicated**. The Dissemination Strategy of CALIPER should be the main measure to maximise the impact of the Project and has to realise three key aspects: (1) Communicate information about the project and the societal challenge it addresses, (2) Disseminate information on the project results to the concerned communities and (3) Enhance exploitation and sustainability of the CALIPER's results.

In this regard, the objectives of the Strategy can be enlisted as follows:

- to identify target groups and analyze their communication needs
- to establish core messages of the project, to be disseminated to the target groups
- to establish and maintain mechanisms for effective and timely dissemination and communication
- to coordinate all levels and types of dissemination and communication in relation to the project
- to define timing of dissemination activities
- to define partners' responsibilities in dissemination activities
- to prepare the ground for ensuring sustainability after its completion
- to introduce a clear and effective monitoring and evaluation procedure for the actions to be carried out

2.2 Messages

This section refers to the properties of the dissemination and communication messages. In order to meet the aforementioned objectives, the content of the varying disseminative efforts has to follow some defined features, meaning that, the present report has to set the tone in terms of **what messages should be promoted**.

Based on the CALIPER's Grant Agreement, the messages to be disseminated and/or communicated need to entail the project's vision in a pertinent and comprehensive way, **highlighting the importance to implement Gender Equality Plans in order to link Research and Innovation for Gender Equality and enhance female researchers' role in STEM**.

What is more, the content needs to be crafted in a **gender-sensitive language**, which means that information should be characterized by **neutral and inclusive terms**. The use of plural number should be opted as the most adequate, while referring to both female and male agents can be made according to the context of each specific message, when necessary.

In addition, each involved RPO/RFO of the Project is assigned to promote CALIPER inside their own structures and to their respective innovation ecosystems comprised by relative stakeholders. Hence the information has to be created entailing **both the essential message of CALIPER as well as messages tailored to the needs and the certain characteristics of each RPO/RFO**. In such terms, crafting messages in the partners native language should be consider a quite purposeful option as well.

Last but not least, the messages of CALIPER should be based on the **produced knowledge** during the different phases of the project and **reflect important moments and achievements through its lifecycle**. Therefore, dissemination and communication content can derive from **important deliverable reports of the project**, such as 'D3.4 Final GEPs', 'D5.5 CALIPER Charter' and the set of Policy Briefings Deliverables of WP6. Also, the establishment of GEP Working Groups, the setup of CALIPER's Research and Innovation Hubs and the initiation of Female Innovation events by project partners are **milestones** which should be communicated.

2.3 Target Audience

To accurately deploy the Dissemination Strategy, it is essential to identify to **whom CALIPER messages will be channeled**.

The Dissemination Strategy of CALIPER is constructed based on the Grant Agreement to address **four target groups** in order to ensure that the Project results will reach the widest possible audiences: 1) **Research communities in Academia** (internal and external), 2) **Policy makers** (national and EU), 3) **Business innovators** and 4) **Citizens, society**.

In addition, the target audiences can be further classified by **two main levels**. On the one side, the **Internal Target Audiences** comprise the structures of the involved RPOs/RFOs, **particularly researchers, management and administrative employees, students and academic staff members** that will have a key role during GEP development and implementation. On the other side the **External Target Audiences** include external stakeholders of the partner RPOs and RFOs who can leverage gender equality measures. Such audiences can be found in **Academia** sector with its STEM Research communities, in **Government** structures run by Policy Makers, in **Business sector** where Innovators are active and in **Civil Societies** where CALIPER Partners are based.

Figure 1: CALIPER Dissemination and Communication Target Audiences

In order for CALIPER to attain an effective engagement with the identified External Audiences, the project adopts the Quadruple Helix approach. Essentially, this approach is an effort to realise direct dialogue and collaboration between the four categories of the external target audiences of the project having the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs coordinating such engagement through the Research & Innovation Hubs (R&I Hubs) that are going to be established.

Figure 2: CALIPER Quadruple Helix Approach

The R&I Hubs will be formed by CALIPER's RPOs/RFOs at regional and national levels, comprising a balance of research and academia, government, business and civil society stakeholders. Leveraging their well-established networks the RPOs/RFOs of CALIPER are going to serve as networks of light structure to communicate the existing collaborations at each ecosystem, to identify common challenges and carry out **joint efforts of promoting gender equality as a mark of excellence and a driving force of innovation**.

Hence the role of the R&I Hubs of each CALIPER RPO/RFO is to **create ties** with those actors who will facilitate the uptake of structural change that the Project seeks and the institutionalisation of its best practices for gender balance.

2.4 Tools Methods & Channels

To effectively promote the aforementioned messages and address **how they will reach the target audiences**, CALIPER has to select what kind of tools, methods and channels are going to be utilised. Various online and offline means, direct and indirect, are necessary to make the project activities and results available to the target groups.

Such methods include online options (website, emails, social media), mass media and networks (media presence, social networks, partners' networks etc.), or offline tangible actions, like events, posters, brochures etc. Depending on the project's audiences the adequate set of methods is going to **be jointly employed**.

Below, there is a detailed description of the tools and channels that CALIPER will utilize during its lifecycle.

2.4.1 Visual Identity

It comprises several features and elements that are necessary for project's promotion and representation, including visual and textual key points:

Logo: first and foremost, it is essential that CALIPER has a notable and memorable visual cue. CALIPER's logo serves as the project's first connection with the audiences and should bring in their minds CALIPER's message. Thus, a coherent visual identity is developed for the project, to trademark the partners' work in any electronic and/or print material.

Templates: aligned with the logo's role, a specified set of format characteristics is fundamental. A great volume of deliverables, presentations and reports produced by project Partners is going to be disseminated, so a defined template is prepared, in order to ensure professional diligence and compliance with EU's guidelines to all the project's documents and communications.

Offline material: CALIPER is projected to hold a great number of events during its lifecycle in varying formats and in many different locations. Each RPO/RFO is going to actualise its own events following the planning of CALIPER's unfolding. Thus, offline material such as posters, banners, leaflets and brochures for audience's communication is required.

2.4.2 Media Content

The Project is expected to produce a significant volume of media related material which is going to serve its dissemination and communication purposes. As the awareness fostering on Gender equality in STEM fields is a key expectation for CALIPER, it should be considered optimum to have CALIPER's media content featured in the communication channels of involved RPOs/RFOs (i.e. Organisations' websites and social media), as well as in Mass Media.

Press Releases: Press releases will refer to pivotal project events or relevant milestones. Such media material will be published on project's website, on CALIPER's social media platforms and through press contacts of

the partner organizations; translation of the content to Partner's native languages will be conducted in order to increase the reach in regional/national level. CALIPER will disseminate **a total of 25 Press Releases**

Newsletters: This option is suitable for dissemination and communication purposes, due to its direct and periodic fashion. Also, media organisations can receive CALIPER newsletters, which will enable project to **be mediated** to stakeholders via credible platforms of high prominence.

The circulation will take place **approximately every six months** through mailing lists and contact databases accumulated by Projects Partners. The content will feature information pieces about project's efforts progressions, significant milestones reached, and news about synergies with relevant projects, planned activities and events of CALIPER.

All versions of the newsletters will be prepared in English and distributed digitally through the platform of MailChimp. It is among the largest marketing automation platforms of the world, with advanced analytics and multipart Email Delivery (both the HTML and plain-text versions of an email).

Videos: A part of the Dissemination Strategy of the Project is the creation of **9 promotional videos** to be used internally at each RPO/RFOs and at external level, to raise the awareness, generate debate and complement actions on supporting female researchers. These **Role Model** Videos will present researchers with different cultural and scientific backgrounds in the STEM area, to highlight the institutional and cultural barriers they faced in their path to become researchers/professors/ deans in STEM and what motivated them.

Those videos will be promoted through different channels as an extra tool to raise awareness (i.e. press releases) and they will be fully available on the project website as well as on CALIPER social media channels.

2.4.3 Online Channels

Website: The project's [website](#) operates as the major source about the project's identity, goals and actions, from which every stakeholder category can be informed. In other words, CALIPER website is a central dissemination and communication tool of the project providing the main results of the CALIPER research and outcomes. In particular, the CALIPER website aims at:

- Providing information about the project, its main objective, knowledge, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which CALIPER will participate, information about project partners and related projects introduction with a link to their websites, subscription to project's newsletter, social networks and contact info.
- Present the information about the entire process that RPOs/RFOs will follow to design and develop GEPs, as well as the further achievements on structural changes.
- Presenting information to stakeholders so that they will understand the reasons to get involved and how they can participate in the project's activities.

Social Media: Social media platforms are a much-needed part of CALIPER Dissemination Strategy, as they allow engaging interested audience with the project and representing its actions via an interactive and direct platform of communication. Through social media, CALIPER can manage a steady flow of information towards diverse audiences during its development and communicate continuously the outcomes of Partners' work together with noteworthy information pieces relevant to the Project's scope.

The CALIPER Dissemination Strategy has chosen to utilize social media accounts on [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#), Using content that matches the structural affordances of each platform and features SEO characteristics (e.g. relevant hashtags) combined with the partners' already existing accounts, CALIPER accounts are going to be used to increase project's visibility in social networking sites.

In this regard, CALIPER has already realised its **first social media campaign on Twitter** forming synergies with EU-supported Projects that are also active on addressing gender equality topics. Since March 2, CALIPER Twitter account, [@CaliperEU](#), has taken part to the campaign **#COMMIT2GENDERRING**. The goal has been to communicate the commitment towards gender equality of the RPOs, RFOs, NGOs and SMEs involved in EU2020 projects. The campaign was organised by Horizon2020 Project ACTonGender and CALIPER was involved along with 10 more sister-projects.

The campaign featured content illustrating what are the expected changes on gender equality for Research Organisations to be pursued through their participation in EU projects. In particular, CALIPER promoted content regarding its 9 RPOs and RFOs. The campaign lasted until March 8, the International Women’s Day; during this period the Project had the chance to kick start its social media presence in an engaging way making sure of its visibility and attracting adequate audiences as it formed synergies with sister-projects.

The timing of the campaign helped CALIPER to make an effective kick-start of its social media presence, since during the first week of March CALIPER was able to count 5.4K impressions.

Figure 3: Tweet activity from 2/3/2020 to 8/3/2020

Figure 4: Tweet engagement from 2/3/2020 to 8/3/2020

As a result, the Twitter profile of the project managed to accumulate audience and a considerable amount of visibility on early stage, given that the social media accounts of the project have been set up along with project’s website during February 2020.

Figure 5: Tweet Highlights March 2020

2.4.4 Events

In CALIPER Project, events are fueling an integral part of the process and they afford a significant capacity for dissemination and communication actions. The distribution of audiences between internal and external levels, as well as the establishment of Research and Innovation Hubs are two aspects of significant influence for the events organisation. Therefore, the following elaboration on the CALIPER events is enlisted:

Events included to the Tasks of WP5 towards the Engagement, Change Management and Sustainability: The table below presents the specific events that are addressing the engagement of internal and external target audiences with CALIPER. Also, their timeframe and the connection to project’s WPs and Tasks is provided. The role of dissemination efforts in regard to these events is to assist on their promotion and coverage.

Events	Description	Timeframe	Relation to other Tasks and WPs
Regular Internal GEP WGs meetings in each RPO/RFO (T5.1)	Link GEP Working Groups with higher-middle management and staff	Periodically, no specified date is applied	This activity belongs to T5.1 and related to T5.3 Organise GEP Working Groups activities And T6.2 Promote RPO/RFO activities internally to each institution
Joint CALIPER Female Innovation events in each RPO/RFO (T5.2)	Create strong links between the R&I Hubs of involved RPOs/RFO and their local/national innovation ecosystems	M23	This activity belongs to T5.2 and is connected to T1.3, T1.4 and T2.2 of WP1 and WP2 . And to T6.3 Promote RPO/RFO activities to targeted external stakeholders

Organisation of an Internal dedicated workshop with GEP WGs (T5.3) and support of internal raising awareness activities of WGs	Elaborate on the results of T1.3 and T1.4	M1-M48	This activity belongs to T5.3 and it is connected to T1.3 and T1.4 of WP1 And to T6.2 Promote RPO/RFO activities internally to each institution
Three rounds of webinar sessions in each RPO/RFO (T5.3)	In depth elaboration on facts, arguments, tools and strategies to address each one of the three ERA objectives on gender equality	M16, M28, M36	This activity belongs to T5.3 and it is connected to T6.2 Promote RPO/RFO activities internally to each institution
Dedicated Sustainability Workshops in each RPO/RFO	Offer support to partner RFO/RPOs in developing Sustainability Plans for the designed GEPs	M29	This activity belongs to T5.4
Organisation of Gender Equality webinars by each RPO/RFO	Present CALIPER Charter and GEPs outcomes to external RPOs/RFOs	M48	This activity belongs to T5.4 and it is connected to T6.3 Promote RPO/RFO activities to targeted external stakeholders

Table 1: Engagement Events - WPS

Events entailed into the WP6 of Dissemination and Communication: In addition, to the above events, the Dissemination Strategy of CALIPER elaborates on events that are part of the overall dissemination and communication of the project and its scope. The following table enlists such events and provides their timeframe, as well as their relation to the WPs and Tasks of CALIPER.

Events	Description	Timeframe	Relation to other Tasks and WPs
Promotional campaign in each RPO/RFO including an internal info session (T6.2)	Promote RPO/RFO GEP elaboration to the institution	M16	This activity belongs to T6.2 and related to T5.3 Organise GEP Working Groups activities
One public info sessions in each RPO/RFO (T6.3)	To present project's insights to external stakeholders, that is members of R&I Hubs.	M1-M48	This activity belongs to T6.3 and is connected to T1.3, T1.4 and T2.2 of WP1 and WP2 that will result to the establishment of R&I Hubs
Half-day event on role models in Brussels, (T6.3)	This sub-task is an activity that will coincide with the kick start of R&I Hubs	The timeframe will be set by the Brussels event	This activity belongs to T6.3 and it is connected T1.3, T1.4 and T2.2 of WP1 and WP2 that will result to the establishment of R&I Hubs

Final CALIPER conference (T6.4)	To present the overall outcomes of the project and conclude its actions. Also, to disseminate Charter	M48	This activity belongs to T6.4 and it will serve as the finalization of CALIPER's actions throughout the WPs
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Table 2: Dissemination Event – WP6

Events of 3rd Parties: A significant volume of Conferences, workshops, fora and other events are being held every year to address gender topics as well as broader thematic on the STEM areas. It is then of great purpose for CALIPER Consortium Members, to seek the participation to such events, in order to disseminate the Project and interact with influential Stakeholders from the pool of its external target audiences. To provide a few examples, the table below includes 3rd party events to which CALIPER Partners can attend.

A/A	Event Title	Type	Location	Date
1	3rd International Conference on Gender Research	Conference	Reading, United Kingdom	April 2020
2	Women in STEM Conference	Conference	London, United Kingdom	May 2020
3	19th Annual STS Conference Graz 2020 "Critical Issues in Science, Technology and Society Studies"	Conference	Graz, Austria	May 2020
4	XI European Conference on Gender Equality in Higher Education	Conference	Madrid, Spain	September 2020
5	Gender Roles and their Impact in Academia	Conference	Heidelberg, Germany	October 2020

Table 3: 3rd Party Events

The aforementioned Conferences afford a two-fold opportunity for disseminative actions. On the one side, the actual networking during such events where multiple stakeholders of CALIPER's target audiences are present constitutes a noteworthy method to increase Project's reach, thus creating further awareness about the goal of institutionalising structural changes in favour of gender equality. On the other side, the submission of conference papers to such events is a common procedure, which, in the case of CALIPER, should be considered a purposeful option, so that knowledge produced through Project's lifecycle can be disseminated via a scientifically curated fashion towards target audiences that can leverage it.

Throughout the progression of the Project, upcoming events are going to be identified and initiatives will be taken from CALIPER Partners in order to attend as many 3rd party events as possible for networking purposes and dissemination of Project's key results.

Synergy events: European Commission has placed significant support to efforts for the establishment of Gender Equality as a Pan-European characteristic feature in a multitude of sectors. Research and Innovation as well as Higher Education are areas where specific attention has been paid to this end and a variety of EU-supported Projects are active. Hence, CALIPER Project is going to invest in collaboration ties with sister-projects for mutual promotion, growth of awareness on Gender Equality efforts and sharing of insights drawn from the derived outcomes. This means that CALIPER will seek to be present in disseminative and networking activities that are going to be organised by projects of similar scope.

2.4.5 Publications/academic dissemination strategy

Project Publications constitute a dissemination tool that informs on the projects' procedures, methodologies and outcomes. Also, it is important to note that is a major manner to meet the guidelines of Horizon2020 regarding the dissemination of funded projects. Hence, the projected body of reports conducted by project partners, not only is going to fuel CALIPER's development but also will facilitate its dissemination planning. This category consists of two overlapping elements:

Deliverable reports: Throughout CALIPER's duration a significant volume of Deliverable Reports is going to be developed and made publicly available. This material is valuable in terms of effective dissemination of the project's contribution to Gender Equality promotion, thus it is going to be disclosed in platforms where it will be able to reach adequate audiences, such as researchers and pundits of gender issues. In particular, the deliverable reports are planned to be uploaded on two interlinked open access repositories supported by European Commission, Zenodo and OpenAir. The role of these platforms is to accumulate and secure accessibility for knowledge that derives from projects like CALIPER community in [Zenodo](#) and maintain a reliable citation database of such material (OpenAir).

Scientific publications: Drawing from the above report material, the Project partners will be able to conduct scholarly content and publish it in the international scientific literature, when possible. The participation to international conferences and events, as mentioned above, affords CALIPER partners the ability to prepare and disseminate papers that elaborate on engendering STEM areas based on the produced knowledge by Project's procedures. All partners are able to conduct academic publications and all publications will be collected in the aforementioned dedicated spaces for open access/download or as link to the scientific magazine that were published.

CALIPER scientific publication policy: The Consortium will respect Article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement with regards to "**Open access to scientific publications**". Each beneficiary will ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

It is a requirement that an acknowledgement of the financial contribution from the EU Horizon 2020 Programme is included in all publications/presentations as follows:

The present study was funded through the Project CALIPER "Linking research and innovation for gender equality " of the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 873134.

For the proper and more effective identification of opportunities to contribute to scientific knowledge and international literature, that can take place via the participation of the CALIPER consortium in conferences and workshops, CALIPER partners have developed an online list of upcoming conferences, listing them according to the area of focus, the date of the conference, the country of venue, fees, possibility to submit a publication, the corresponding partner that should participate and such other information.

Furthermore, the table below will be used to keep track on the partner's publications:

Lead Author	Co-author(s)	Manuscript title	Manuscript purpose/scope	Keywords	Proposed journal(s)	Approved (by who?)

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Table 4: Template for monitoring partners' publications

The table below summarizes the deliverables that could potentially lead to the publication of a scientific paper relevant to the project results regarding to the GEP design stages for maximizing the project's impact and achieve a greater outreach to the targeted stakeholders:

GEP development stage	Deliverable	Milestone	Month	Responsible partner
Analysing and assessing the state-of-play in the institution	D1.2 Internal Gender Equality Assessments Results	MS3 End of the internal assessments	M12	VIL and partners
Analysing and assessing the state-of-play in the Research and Innovation ecosystems.	D1.3 Gender analysis of research and innovation ecosystems and reports from the local R&I Hubs	MS4 Analysis of external conditions and factors	M12	SV and partners
Setting up a Gender Equality Plan	D2.2 Reporting results of multi-stakeholder dialogues	MS4 Scenarios developmen	M15	ULB and partners
Setting up a Gender Equality Plan	D2.3 GEPs	MS4 GEPs Design Finalized	M18	SV and partners
Implementing a Gender Equality Plan	D3.1 GEPs implementation during phase 1	MS7 End of implementation phase 1 & End of implementation phase 2	M42	UZG and partners
Monitoring progress and evaluating a Gender Equality Plan	D4.4 Summative Evaluation Results	MS9 Initiation of Summative evaluation	M44	SV and all partners

Table 5: Potential topics for scientific publications

2.5 Partners' Role

The dissemination and communication of CALIPER should be taken into account as a collective effort, meaning that all partners may contribute to the impact maximisation which is the optimum goal. Hence, this strategy pays attention to each Consortium Member profile and argues that through the coalescing of the diverse capacities that CALIPER partners feature, an effective dissemination and communication course is attainable.

2.5.1 SMEs

In addition to the project coordination, ViLabs is leading the WP6 on Dissemination and Communication as the SME features extensive experience on the dissemination of H2020 Projects. Through the leading role, ViLabs is responsible for implementing, coordinating and monitoring the aggregate of the dissemination and communication activities that are going to take place during CALIPER's lifecycle. That is, ViLabs is going to craft and update the Dissemination Strategy of CALIPER, set up its online channels, create the online and offline materials needed for disseminative and communicative purposes, coordinate partners in regards to their own disseminative and communicative efforts and keep track of such actions.

Based on the specialization on social innovation, Smart Venice provides gender expert knowledge for the actualization of CALIPER's actions. Therefore, the SME is engaged with the dissemination and communication of the project by securing that context and content-wise the effort to promote CALIPER and propagate its impact follows the adequate criteria for Gender Equality promotion and inclusiveness.

2.5.2 Pan-European Professional Association

The YAE is a pan-European initiative of outstanding young scientists for networking, scientific exchange and science policy. The YAE is organized as a bottom-up initiative of a dynamic and innovative group of recognized European young scientists and scholars with outspoken views about science and science policy. YAE provides input and advice from a younger generation's perspective – a vital requirement to shape EU-wide Science Policy for the prospering of science in Europe for future generations. YAE can enhance the project dissemination via its network of researchers throughout Europe, and their links to other national and international Academies, including other European Young Academies and the Academia Europa. Hence, the partner is going to contribute to the dissemination of CALIPER towards external target audiences, especially in research communities in Academia.

2.5.3 RPOs/RFOs

The Research Organisations involved in CALIPER are the central points around which the whole project unfolds. Due to the fundamental goal of structural change in these institutions via Gender Equality Plans, it is consequent that these CALIPER partners are going to play a significant role in terms of project's dissemination and communication actions. Both at internal and at external level, the involved RPOs/RFOs are going to implement a series of informative, awareness fostering and engagement actions, all of which correlate with the dissemination and communication purposes of the project.

Essentially, these CALIPER Partners constitute the key intermediates through which the project's scope and results are going to be targeted to regional and national audiences. In this regard, the Dissemination Strategy elaborates on the following aspects:

Communications resources of involved RPOs/RFOs: At a preliminary stage, CALIPER Dissemination Strategy has conducted a mapping of the communications resources at each Research Organisation involved in the project. CALIPER partner, ULB, that is assigned to carry out the Intra-institutional Internal communications of the Project has conducted a survey to outline the capacities among CALIPER Consortium to disseminate project's information at internal and external level. This action has been a firm initial step to evaluate where CALIPER's dissemination and communication prospects stand in overall.

According to the results, there is a common ground for dissemination of CALIPER through the websites and the social media accounts of all the involved Organisations. The majority of the RPOs/RFOs circulate newsletters, where CALIPER information can be featured, nevertheless there is a need to also address the information dissemination at the few Organisations that have not reported a newsletter. Even though, all

RPOs/RFOs run a calendar for communication of future their events, no specific event on gender issues is held on most of the Organisations, while only few groups active on gender topics exist on the involved RPOs/RFOs. Hence, CALIPER’s GEP Working Groups of each RPO/RFO and the events mentioned in this report are going to play a significant role and the Dissemination Strategy has to pay enough attention on disseminating and communicating them.

Below, the aggregated results are presented:

Five (5) out of the nine (9) RPOs/RFOs have a space dedicated in their intranet. (i.e. website dedicated only to staff members)

All nine (9) RPOs/RFOs have an online calendar and/or agenda where future events are communicated

Figure 6: Intranet capacity

Figure 7: Online calendar and/or agenda for future events

All nine (9) RPOs/RFOs have their own Website

Six (6) Organisations are regularly sending a newsletter

Figure 8: Website capacity

Figure 9: Newsletter capacity

Four (4) RPOs/RFOs have a printed and/or online magazine distributed to the Organisation's community

Only two (2) Organisations report an internal network responsible for communicating gender-related issues

Figure 10: Printed and/or online Magazine

Figure 11: Internal network for communication of gender-related issues

The majority of RPOs/RFOs does not have an active group working on gender equality, which CALIPER can contact to share information

Currently, an event on gender-related topics is held only in two (2) Organisations

Figure 12: Group on Gender Equality

Figure 13: Events on gender-related topics currently organised

Facebook is used by all 9 RPOs/RFOs, while LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube are also used by the majority

Only three (3) Organisations report contacts on media interested on covering gender-related topics

Figure 14: Social Media capacities

Figure 15: Media Contacts

The accumulated data provide an overview of the resources available on each Organisation, in which CALIPER is planning its dissemination and communication actions. Therefore, CALIPER will tailor the strategy upon the reported capacity resources.

As a result, the Dissemination Strategy will focus on leveraging the sufficiency of Organisations’ online channels to attain high visibility, while it will work towards mitigating the reported shortage of real life events and agents on gender-related issues through efforts to promote CALIPER’s procedures and events and establish them as a point of reference on the Project’s RPOs/RFOs.

Engagement of Internal Target Audiences: Drawing from the aforementioned goal to integrate CALIPER activities to the involved RPOs/RFOs, an important note should be made at this point regarding the engagement events that are part of WP5 of Engagement, Change Management and Sustainability. As mentioned earlier, there is a pre-defined set of activities for the engagement of the internal audiences on each RPO/RFO, that the dissemination of CALIPER is assigned to assist. Hence, the Dissemination Strategy annotates that the collaboration between the implementing partners and Dissemination Leader, ViLabs, is the key factor for successful roll out of such activities. The organizing Partner is going to be in direct communication with ViLabs to make sure the adequate dissemination material (i.e. press releases, leaflets, social media campaigns, etc.) is prepared to meet the needs of each engagement activity. What is more, common efforts will be made in order to point out these activities should be disseminated inside the hosting Organisations and to their regional/national communities.

Engagement of External Target Audiences: In addition to the internal dissemination, the engagement activities of RPOs/RFOs are going to address the key stakeholder audiences of their innovation ecosystems. The role of each Organisation’s Research and Innovation Hub is considered fundamental for the engagement of the identified Stakeholders with CALIPER, as the networking dialogues are projected to take place trough CALIPER Hubs. In this regard, the dissemination efforts of the project need to provide enough promoting assistance to such activities by elaborating tailored messages and all the necessary content in online and

offline forms. Again, such efforts must be a product of effective collaboration by the implementing RPOs/RFOs and the dissemination Leader, ViLabs.

On the following table, an overview of each RPO/RFO initial ecosystem is enlisted. It constitutes an initial capacity mapping of the ecosystems of which the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs are part. Given the highlighted collaboration aspect between dissemination and communication efforts and the engagement activities the present deliverable's overview is going to be enhanced by a further elaboration which is going to be carried out on 'D5.2 - Report on existing identified opportunities of facilitating the engagement and access to the market of STEM researchers'.

Partner RPO/RFO	Ecosystem Engagement and research transfer to market
UZG – FER	<p>The Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of University of Zagreb (FER) is Croatia's leading academic and research institution in the field of electrical engineering, computing, and information and communication technology and is integrated and competitive in European higher education and research area.</p> <p>The Faculty has active projects with big national companies, such as HEP, Hrvatski Telekom, Ericsson Nikola Tesla, HRT etc. The Faculty also actively supports student entrepreneurship and various kinds of startups. As for national authorities, the Faculty is funded by the Ministry of Science and Education of Croatia, and many of the research projects are funded by the Croatian Science Foundation.</p>
SRNSF	<p>The Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation (SRNSF) is a key player in Georgian innovation ecosystem, especially via our grants for applied research. SRNSF has close ties with different organizations.</p> <p>Georgia's Innovation and Technology Agency (GITA) is an organisation that is closely linked with the innovation ecosystem and operates under the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia. GITA is an important partner of SRNSF and has signed a memorandum of understanding with our Foundation.</p> <p>Moreover, the National Intellectual Property Center of Georgia SAKPATENTI is another major partner of SRNSF which is a governmental agency – a legal entity of public law.</p>
STU BA	<p>Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU BA) collaborates with different organisations: EAI Slovakia – Branch of European Alliance for Innovation in Slovakia; Eureka Cluster – Smart Advanced Manufacturing Program. Clusters bring together large companies along with SMEs, research institutes and universities to develop technologies for important sectors such as ICT, energy or water; DAC – Danubius Academic Consortium; Autoclusters; ZAP Autocluster; Local public authority: City Hall Trnava.</p> <p>These institutions still have no gender equality policies or initiatives. Cooperation could address the following issues: better involving leadership in gender equality within the networked stakeholders; gender-sensitive communication; maternity/paternity leave provisions; childcare provisions.</p>
ULB	<p>Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB) is embedded in an ecosystem of research and economic actors in the French speaking community of Belgium and contributes to the development of human resources at a regional, national and international levels. Indeed, ULB has strong ties with the following structures, contributes to their funding programs</p>

	<p>and has been traditionally “feeding” through scientific excellence, knowledge and innovation the research-driven developments in the Regions.</p> <p>Inversely, ULB researchers benefit from economic support and partner networks to continue excelling in frontier research and innovation activities: The Walloon region which has launched its competitiveness clusters (clusters.wallonie.be); The Brussels Region which funds market-oriented research through Innoviris; The French Speaking community which funds fundamental research through FNRS (www.fnrs.be).</p> <p>ULB has also established long-standing collaboration with Walloon and Brussels regional industry & technology transfer clusters, such as the Walloon Union of Enterprises, the Walloon competitiveness clusters, The Agence pour l’Entreprise & l’ Innovation, Actiris, LIEU network, GSK. Actiris: The Diversity unit of Actiris offers free guidance to public and private organizations localised in Brussels for the “elaboration, implementation, evaluation and the follow-up” of their diversity plan. Innoviris: Innoviris finances initiatives that aim at promoting science and innovation. GSK: One of health-care company GSK’s main responsibilities is to “inspire, educate, recruit and develop” the next generation of STEM scientists.</p>
NTUA – ECE	<p>The School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of National Technological University of Athens (ECE) is embedded in an ecosystem of research and innovation and contributes to the creation of new technology both on a National and a European level.</p> <p>The School fosters the engagement of high-quality research personnel in laboratories covering the broad range of the electrical and computer engineering discipline. The School is active in programmes financed by the European Commission (such as Horizon 2020), as well as those funded by national sources (e.g. the Greek General Secretariat of Research and Technology). Given the applied nature of its research activities, the School has collaborated with several public (e.g. Ministries, Local Governments) and private sector stakeholders (e.g. ICT Businesses, Public Utilities, Industry Associations). The School also has strong links with other academic institutions built through common activities (such as the Athens University of Economics and Business and the University of Piraeus). The School also oversees the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS). The ICCS performs research and also provides scientific consulting services to the public and private sector both in Greece and abroad.</p> <p>Currently, ECE (and the ICCS) has not yet initiated any GEPs. Gender awareness and the presence of relevant policies in most of the stakeholders in the ECE-NTUA ecosystem are varied, but are generally low. Nevertheless, it can provide a suitable environment for the development of innovative know-how in the field of Gender Equality Policies in STEM RPOs and RFOs.</p>
IRB	<p>The Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB) is located in the Barcelona Science Park. Hosting 4 world-class research institutions, 10 foundations related to research and over 70 companies, the PCB is a centre in which first-class public research converges with the private sector in a stimulating entrepreneurial scientific environment. IRB has established institutional collaboration agreements with major research hospitals in the Barcelona area.</p> <p>From an industrial standpoint, IRB is highly proactive in fostering entrepreneurial activities and spinoff creation. IRB is a member of BIST, which aims to promote excellent</p>

	<p>and innovative research in an environment in which diversity, equality and inclusion are valued and promoted. The close collaboration between the BIST centres leverages the exchange of good practices, the co-designing of GEP policies and also the design and implementation of joint gender equality measures.</p> <p>Moreover, IRB has strong links with the Asociación de Mujeres Investigadoras y Tecnólogas (AMIT). IRB is a member of the CERCA Institute, the network of public research centres promoted by the Catalan Government. which represents a unique opportunity for the exchange of good practices and the co-design of GEP policies. The Innovation Department at IRB also has a good relationship with Biocat, and with “la Caixa” Banking Foundation.</p>
<p>UEFISCDI</p>	<p>The innovation ecosystem in which the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI) activates include quadruple-helix actors, as following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public institutions – the core collaboration is with the Ministry of National Education and the Ministry of Research and Innovation; • Research and academia – these types of organisations are part of the beneficiaries of the funds for RDI managed by UEFISCDI; • Private sector – innovative companies (companies with NACE code for research) are part of the beneficiaries of the funds for RDI managed by UEFISCDI; • Non-governmental organisations – take part in the dialogue for developing public policies supporting innovation (e.g. Association of Research Managers and Administrators in Romania, RARMA). <p>Even if the legislative context in which UEFISCDI operates is rather unsupportive, as the analysis of national policies indicated, this informal commitment of stakeholders towards promoting gender equality is a prerequisite for their interest and support for co-developing a comprehensive GEP which could also serve as a model for their own work.</p>
<p>YU</p>	<p>Based on its previous project and research experiences at local and international levels, Yasar University (YU) has a large network of stakeholders including NGOs, HEIs, business and individuals. YU has been collaborating with around 500 different institutions in the frame of the EU funded projects and has more than 200 partner universities. At local and national level, the relevant stakeholders for this project are:</p>

- -Union of Women Associations in Izmir: The Union of Women Associations is one of the strongest unions working for women in Turkey. The association specifically works on increasing women’s participation in decision-making mechanisms. g.
- -Turkish Women Union. It was established in 2 February 1924 with the aim of ensuring that women have political rights and that they participate equally in social life.
- -Aegean Industrialists and Businessmen Association (ESIAD): was founded on 16 March 1992 under the leadership of pioneering industrialists and businessmen in the Aegean Region ESIAD is a non-governmental organization believing that free enterprise plays a critical role in economic development.
- -Izmir Metropolitan Municipality Directorate of Women Studies: the directorate collects gender equality data in Izmir for finding solutions in the Gender Equality Commission of the Municipality and provides gender equality and women’s rights trainings to citizens and local stakeholders.
- -Ege University Research and Application Centre of Woman Studies: EKAM encourages, supports and publishes researches done on the topics of women’s existence in social existence, women’s situation in labour market and violence against women.
- -TOG (Community Volunteers Association) Gender Mainstreaming Program: It is integrating gender perspective into several intervention areas in order to establish gender equality at all levels within the Community Volunteers Foundation.

UNLIE

The ecosystem engagement has been occurred in the departments and in the ISUFI excellence school of University of Salento (UNILE).

In particular the ISUFI main mission has been to promote and increase high-level interdisciplinary under- and post-graduate educational programs, based on principles of residentiality and internationalization. ISUFI runs projects and collaborations with big national companies and PMI, like Systea spa, Dhitech scarl, the Qube aps, Innovaal scarl, STMicroelectronics, San Raffaele Hospital Research Center, Reply, Noemalife, Matrix s.r.l., LPT_Measure srl, Exprivia. It also collaborates with the Institute for Microelectronics and Microsystems IMM (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). ISUFI takes part every year in the “Festival dell’Innovazione”.

Finally, ISUFI collaborates to the activities supported by the Italian Department for Equal Opportunities for the promotion of equal opportunities. The stakeholders do not have gender equality policies or initiatives ongoing. In fact, the policies for UNILE developed through the project will help stakeholders, PMI and new STARTUPS to develop initiatives to increase GEP policies.

Table 6: Ecosystem Engagement and research transfer to market per partner

3 Monitoring & Evaluation

To complement and effectively assess the dissemination and communication efforts, the Dissemination Strategy features specific monitoring and evaluation aspects. The goal is to provide concrete evidence about the effectiveness of the efforts carried out and provide insights on how to amplify the reach and impact of CALIPER.

The knowledge produced is going to steer CALIPER's Dissemination Strategy towards the most effective course. As a result, the periodic review and update of project's Dissemination Strategy will depend on the data sourced in the Dissemination and Communication Activities Reports. In this way, the best practices will be identified, while attention will be given to re-define options of less impact.

What is more, CALIPER adopts a quality assurance and risk management procedure, which is addressed by 'D7.2 Quality Assurance - Risk Management plan'. The deliverable acts as a reference about the overall management of the project throughout its duration and elaborates on the approach to identify and mitigate existing and potential risks that may hinder project's implementation. Hence any potential setback regarding the dissemination and communication actions presented in the current strategy, is taken into account by the concurrent deliverable. In brief, the potential risks, including those related to dissemination and communication, are classified to operational, time and competence risks, as well as force majeure situations.

To this end, VIL as the leader of WP6 is responsible to oversee the progress of CALIPER's dissemination and communication activities and take resolving actions, when needed. The monitoring and evaluation tools of such responsibility are going to assess the CALIPER's efforts in qualitative and quantitative fashion. The procedures to be implemented are the following:

Coordination of actions by ViLabs: Drawing from the aforementioned tools, methods and channels to disseminate and communicate CALIPER, each partner has to implement a specific set of actions. The list of actions comprises pre-defined and scheduled tasks, but also includes partners' individual plans for dissemination and communication activities which due to their nature cannot be precisely pre-organised, like the participation to upcoming conferences and networking events and/or the creation of scholarly publications. Therefore, it is essential that ViLabs communicates regularly with every partner and coordinate the implementation of such actions.

Reporting of actions by all partners: Upon the completion of any form of their assigned dissemination activity, partners have to fill the Dissemination Report Form (*see Annex I*), so that a robust book-keeping of dissemination and communication efforts is made. The form is stored at a dedicated space at Teamwork Repository and partners will use it to provide specific information on the type of their activity and a series of simple, yet necessary, details of it. ViLabs is going to communicate the Report with all project partners in a bi-monthly base in order to collect data about the activities and efforts carried out by each partner.

Moreover, when an opportunity for a dissemination activity emerges, partners need to notify WP6 leader, ViLabs, about it, to document such action accordingly and provide any necessary assistance (e.g. guidelines, tips for better communication etc.).

Statistics of visibility, traffic, reach and engagement rates of CALIPER's website and social media platforms. This will allow partners to better understand the most appropriate timing, communication style and target audience of each message. Furthermore, such metrics are essential for planning re-adjustments.

3.1 KPIs

The above procedures are necessary to be grasped by all partners and implemented accordingly, in order to establish a smooth cooperation since the beginning of the project and all the relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are met. The data collected throughout the monitoring and reporting of CALIPER's

dissemination and communication actions is going to be benchmarked against the measures to maximise impact as they have been set on project's Grant Agreement. The following table includes the core KPIs that have to be attained by the dissemination and communication actions:

Channel	Tool	Purpose	Description	KPIs	Validation
Media	Press Releases	Raise awareness and inform the stakeholders.	A direct announcement/statement to the Media which will communicate project events and activities.	Total of 25 .	Press Releases will be uploaded at project's website.
Online Channels	Website	Raise visibility and inform the stakeholders.	A dedicated page will provide a dissemination channel for the project outputs and documentation and information concerning the project progress.	Take website live featuring information about the project and update the content periodically.	Statistics will be kept through Google Analytics to monitor website's traffic.
	Project Publications	Present results to stakeholders and society.	Public deliverables and scientific papers explain the project objectives strategies and the plan of action.	At least 3 publications per year .	Project Publications will be accessible through CALIPER's dedicated space at Zenodo repository.
	Newsletter	Raise awareness, interest and inform the stakeholders.	To be used to announce the project, develop a profile and give regular updates on its progress. It will be creative making sure that all target groups know how the project is progressing.	1 Issue every 6 months .	Newsletter Issues will be uploaded at project's website.
	Social Media	Raise visibility, interact, promote, and inform the stakeholders	Social Media are playing a promotional role for the project and improve visibility of the results to a wide range of audiences. Regular	Total of 1000 followers.	Statistics will be kept through each platform's analytics to

			posts and updates on project developments, news sharing of best practices increasing engagement and interaction.		monitor followership.
Offline Activities	Promotion materials (brochures, posters, etc.)	Raise awareness and visibility to the stakeholders and promote project events.	Both digital and printed brochures will be created and circulated electronically or printed with simplified messages for the society to present the benefits and impact of the project, with easy to read content.	Create project's brochure and prepare more materials according to project's needs.	Monitoring and reporting of materials preparation and dissemination.
	Conference Presentations	Raise awareness and engage stakeholders and promote project outcomes and events	National and European conferences to share the projects achievements with experts in the field and raise interest among target groups.	At least 10 presentations, along project.	Monitoring and reporting of partners' participation to Events.
	Collaboration with other EU funded projects and/or initiatives	Join forces with similar projects to exchange knowledge on the common challenges we aim to address	Close collaboration with projects active in similar areas to communicate CALIPER's results, exchange knowledge through online and physical meetings	Minimum of 4 collaborations.	Monitoring and reporting of project's synergies.

Table 7: KPIs

What is more, the Dissemination Strategy -as a key component of the WP6 on Dissemination and Communication of CALIPER- takes into account the involvement of this WP to three of the expected impacts that are envisioned for CALIPER. Hence, the dissemination and communication actions that are part of the present strategy play a significant supporting role on successfully reaching short (ST= Month 12), medium (MT= Month 36) and long term (LT= Month 48) outcomes set for projected as below:

Expected Impact	Description	Outcomes	Target Indicators	Timeframe
	Increase the number of research	RPOs/RFOs engaged and influenced by the	More than 80.	LT

Expected Impact 1	organisations and higher education establishments implementing gender equality plans.	project to initiate their own GEPs.		
		External Stakeholders stemming from academia, business sector, government and civil society engaged supporting and further elaborating on the project results for the wider implementation of GEP measures in national ecosystems.	At least 100.	LT
		Project's final Conference with the participation of external RPOs/RFOs and other Stakeholders.	80 participants from minimum of 15 RPOs, 8 RFOs and other Stakeholders such as gender equality experts, professional associations and policy makers.	LT
Expected Impact 3	Improve the gender balance in decision-making bodies in research organisations.	Researchers and academics reached by CALIPER's 9 " Role Model " promotional videos.	At least 600.	MT & LT
Expected Impact 5	Achieve ERA objectives through the implementation of CALIPER GEPs and their medium to long term influence on policymaking.	Policy briefings developed at national and European level.	10 briefings per year (9 national and 1 European).	ST, MT & LT
		Synergies with projects on Gender Equality in Research and/or on Open Science and Innovation.	10 projects.	MT

Table 8: Expected Impacts

Hence the above, the evaluation of the Dissemination Strategy is based on addressing the indicators and the fulfillment of the outcomes that are presented. All partners are responsible to contribute to the efforts to be made in order to successfully reach the planned results. Inner-project communication between partners and ViLabs and timely reporting are the fundamental aspects to the smooth implementation of dissemination and communication actions. In addition, communication among CALIPER partners for valuable information sharing on opportunities for collaborative dissemination of the project is highly encouraged.

Annex I: Dissemination Activities Report Form

Dissemination Report Form

Partner

***Instructions:** To report your activity please copy this template to a new sheet and fill it with the appropriate information. Save it and then re-upload it at Teawork dedicated folder

Type of activity

Title of activity / slogan

Title of the event (if applicable)

Venue (if applicable)

Date

Title of the presentation (if applicable)

url of the activity (if applicable)

url of the publication (if applicable)

Type of audience reached below. Please select more than one type ONLY if applicable, up to a maximum of 3. Please indicate ESTIMATED no of persons reached per type of audience (Requested by EC)						
Research Community	Policy Makers	Industry/Business sector	Society (Customers, Civil groups, general public)	Media	Other	
Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	

Please copy below any photos or copy relevant links (e.g. to videos, presentation files, announcement screenshots, etc.)

Comments

Would you like to report any information about the outcome of the activity in relation to UNITI benefit?

***Event List**

- Organisation of a Workshop or a Networking event
- Participation to a Workshop
- Participation to a Conference
- Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop (Networking events, Exhibitions, Symposia, Webinars etc.)
- Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects (Synergies)
- Training Session
- Press release
- Newsletter
- Scientific and peer reviewed publication (article and/or papers and/or presentation)
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) (Blog entries)
- Media Publications (News pieces, articles etc.)
- Poster
- Flyer
- Social Media
- Website
- Video/Film
- Other

***Partner List**

- VIL
- SM
- UZG
- SRNSF
- STU BA
- YAE
- ULB
- NTUA
- IRB
- UEFIS
- YU
- UNILE

